

Consumer Drivers of Residential Rooftop PV Adoption: A Bibliometric and Science-Mapping Review (2000–2025)

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Abstract

This review examines household adoption behaviour of rooftop solar photovoltaic (PV) systems. Solar PV offers notable environmental, economic, and social benefits, yet the literature lacks a comprehensive overview of its adoption patterns among residents. Using a bibliometric approach, 35 publications from the Scopus database were analysed. Co-citation and co-word techniques were employed to identify historical developments and forecast emerging directions in the field. The findings highlight major themes related to the diffusion of innovation and key motivational factors influencing residential solar PV uptake. Overall, the study enhances understanding of critical determinants shaping adoption behaviour, with both theoretical and practical implications.

Keywords Solar Photovoltaic, Bibliometric Analysis, Sustainable Development, Electric Cooking.

Introduction

The planet is facing severe environmental crises resulting from unsustainable energy use. Excessive dependence on conventional sources has accelerated climate change and the exhaustion of natural resources. The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2023) reports that nearly 2.3 billion people worldwide still lack access to clean cooking technologies, leading to significant health, environmental, and gender-related challenges. To mitigate these threats, renewable energy has become a crucial alternative, with solar photovoltaic (PV) systems playing a central role in this transition. Traditional biomass and kerosene stoves generate household air pollution that causes millions of premature deaths each year, with women and children bearing the greatest burden due to exposure, unsafe fuel collection, and loss of time (WHO, 2024). These combined health, gender, and environmental challenges have shifted clean cooking to the forefront of SDG7 and positioned it as a driver of multiple SDGs on health, equality, climate, and ecosystems (IEA, 2024; Rosenthal et al., 2017).

In this context, solar PV has become a promising clean cooking pathway, complementing alternatives such as LPG, bioethanol, biogas, and advanced biomass stoves. Over the last decade, PV costs have dropped dramatically, with the global weighted-average LCOE for utility-scale systems declining by nearly 89% between 2010 and 2022, reaching USD 0.049/kWh (IRENA, 2023). At the same time, renewable deployment has accelerated, with global PV capacity surpassing 1.6 TW in 2023 and 2.2 TW by the end of 2024 (IEA, 2024). Technological improvements in lithium-ion batteries, power electronics, and system design further enhance feasibility by lowering peak power constraints and enabling solutions ranging from grid-based e-cooking to PV-battery systems tailored for daily household cooking (Leary et al., 2021; Watkins et al., 2017).

Although solar PV presents strong potential for cooking applications, research in

this field remains relatively new, drawing on perspectives from energy engineering, development studies, policy, and environmental sciences. With growing scholarly attention, a bibliometric review offers value by consolidating existing knowledge, identifying leading authors and institutions, tracing emerging themes, mapping global collaborations, and highlighting gaps that impede technological adoption and effective policymaking.

Although numerous reviews have examined solar PV in relation to electrification and thermal uses, limited attention has been given to its role in cooking technologies. Even fewer studies have applied bibliometric techniques to assess research trends, collaborations, and thematic progress in this niche.

Objective of study This paper aims to map the research landscape of solar PV for cooking (2003–2025) using bibliometric and science-mapping techniques. It examines publication trends to track the field's growth, identifies the most influential authors, and highlights major thematic keywords. These insights reveal the intellectual structure of the domain and key drivers shaping its evolution.

Review of Literature

Bibliometric analysis offers a systematic and visual representation of scholarly literature, enabling quantitative evaluation of research trajectories over time. This approach is well established for identifying intellectual structures, thematic evolution, and research dynamics (Blanco-Mesa et al., 2017; Donthu et al., 2021). Its value is especially evident in multidisciplinary domains such as solar PV-based sustainable cooking. To address this gap, the present study applies bibliometric analysis to global research outputs from 2003 to 2025.

Accordingly, this study addresses the following research questions using a bibliometric approach:

RQ1: What is the overall publication trend of research on solar PV for cooking between 2003 and 2025?

RQ2: Who are the most influential authors contributing to this field, and major keywords in this research domain?

To answer the research questions, this study applies bibliometric analysis, a well-established method for quantitatively examining scholarly publications (Beckendorff & Zehrer, 2013). The focus is placed on the growth, intellectual foundations, and thematic evolution of research concerning solar PV technologies for electric cooking. The results contribute to a holistic understanding of the field's progression, while highlighting dominant trends and uncovering areas that require further research.

Methodology

This study applies bibliometric analysis, drawing data from the Scopus databases, with the analysis performed in R (Biblioshiny, version 4.4.2).

1.Database for Retrieving Articles

Scopus was selected as the primary data source owing to its broad coverage of peer-reviewed scholarship, rigorous indexing practices, and strong academic credibility. Their robust citation tracking and detailed metadata make them well-suited for bibliometric analysis.

A comprehensive search was conducted using the following search string in both databases:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("solar PV" AND "electric cooking") OR ("solar photovoltaic" AND "electric cooking") OR ("solar PV" AND "cooking") OR ("solar photovoltaic" AND "cooking") OR ("photovoltaic" AND "e-cooking") OR ("PV" AND "e-cooking"). The data extraction was performed on 06 August 2025, yielding a total of 151

documents. The publication year range was limited to 2000–2025, as bibliographic records on the topic begin from 2003 in both databases.

After refinement based on document type, language and subject area, the dataset was further screened by title and abstract to ensure relevance to the interaction of solar PV. A total of 35 studies were retained as the final dataset for the bibliometric review.

2. Software Used for Analysis

For bibliometric analysis, this study employed Biblioshiny, a user-friendly web interface of the Bibliometrix R package (Lajeunesse, 2016). The platform has become popular in academic research for enabling advanced bibliometric functions without the need for programming expertise (Linnenluecke et al., 2020). Biblioshiny allows seamless integration of data from Scopus, providing comprehensive analyses of authors, documents, sources, and thematic trajectories. It also generates a wide range of visualisations, including co-authorship and collaboration networks, keyword co-occurrence maps, and thematic clusters, that support exploration of a field’s intellectual, conceptual, and social dimensions.

Result and Discussion

Primary Information from the Scopus Database

The table presents core research metrics from Scopus (2003–2025), outlining publication trends, author collaboration, and citation impact. It serves to illustrate research growth, scholarly influence, and collaboration dynamics.

Table 1. Primary Information from the Scopus WOS Database

Description	Results	Description	Results
Main Information		Authors	
Timespan	2003:2025	Authors	123
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	22	Authors of single-authored docs	2
Documents	34	AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Annual Growth Rate %	9.71	Single-authored docs	2
Document Average Age	4.32	Co-Authors per Doc	3.91
Average citations per doc	56.18	International authorships %	23.53
References	2127	Document types	
Document contents		article	30
Keywords Plus (ID)	378	review	4
Author’s Keywords (DE)	142		

Source: Compiled by the researcher using R studio

Performance Analysis

Performance analysis evaluates the research output and influence of authors, institutions, and countries by employing bibliometric measures such as publication counts, authorship patterns, and citation indicators.

Figure 1: demonstrates the annual scientific production on solar PV cooking research shows a slow and inconsistent pattern during the early years (2003–2015), with very few publications appearing. A modest increase begins after 2016, marked by intermittent spikes in output. Noticeable peaks emerge in 2018 and 2022, but the most significant surge occurs in 2023–2024, reflecting heightened academic attention to the subject. This sharp rise in recent years suggests that solar PV cooking has moved from a niche area of study to an

emerging research frontier. Overall, the trend indicates growing recognition of the technology's importance and its potential contributions to sustainable energy transitions.

Figure 1. Annual Scientific Production. Source: By Biblioshiny using R studio

Scientific Mapping

Science mapping provides a means to visualise and analyze the intellectual structure and development of a research field. It applies techniques such as citation analysis, co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, co-word analysis, and co-authorship analysis to reveal influential works, thematic linkages, and collaboration networks (Deng et al., 2021).

Co-authorship analysis explores how research outputs are jointly produced by two or more authors (van Eck et al., 2014). It highlights the strength of connections between scholars based on their shared publications (Enciso-Alfaro, 2023). Figure 2 illustrates a co-authorship network of leading researchers in solar PV applications for sustainable cooking, revealing distinct collaboration clusters. It shows several small, disconnected clusters of researchers working on solar PV for sustainable cooking. The largest and most visible cluster is led by Odoi-Yorke and Opoku, indicating strong collaboration and higher research activity within this group. Other clusters, such as those involving Abubakar & Ivanova, Alsharif & Ahmad, and Barton & Brown, suggest localized or bilateral partnerships. A few authors, like Batchelor and Ahmed, appear isolated, reflecting limited collaboration. Overall, the network highlights a fragmented research landscape, with collaboration concentrated in a few core groups but limited global integration.

central, while socio-economic, cultural, and policy dimensions are less integrated. This imbalance highlights the need for more holistic approaches that connect engineering solutions with social realities.

Conclusion

Overall, this review provides a consolidated understanding of the intellectual and thematic structures of solar PV cooking research. It demonstrates the transition of the field from a niche area to an emerging frontier within sustainable energy studies. By mapping research trends, collaborations, and gaps, this study offers a foundation for guiding scholars, practitioners, and policymakers toward scaling solar PV cooking solutions for sustainable development.

Suggestions for the future Study

Future research should expand the scope to include themes such as gender equity, health impacts, financing mechanisms, and adoption behaviour, which are currently underrepresented. Interdisciplinary and international collaborations are essential to reduce the fragmented nature of existing research networks. Moreover, exploring localised case studies and integrating policy evaluations can strengthen the practical relevance of solar PV cooking research.

Limitation of the Study

A limitation of this study is its reliance on Scopus as the sole data source, which may have excluded relevant literature indexed in other databases or available in grey literature. Additionally, bibliometric methods capture publication patterns and collaborations but may not fully reflect qualitative insights or policy-oriented outcomes.

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